

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING THROUGH MODERN PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES

Khasanova Madina

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Annotation: In this article, we can see the basis of the development and prosperity of the education system in foreign countries and analyze it on the example of several countries.

Key words: education, pedagogical technology, pedagogue, best practices, educational method, learner, moderator, tutor, advisor, facilitator

The purpose of studying the subject "Advanced foreign experiences in modern education and innovative technologies" is to teach students to form a system of knowledge, skills and abilities about advanced foreign experiences in modern education and innovative technologies, and to use modern teaching technology in the educational process. The task of the subject is to form the theoretical and practical knowledge and skills of the listener in this subject.

Education system in Japan

The formation of Japanese education began in 1867-1868. Japan has two tasks: the first is to become rich, and the second is to introduce Western technology into Japanese production, and in order to do this, it was said that the education system should be fundamentally changed. In 1872, the "Law on Education" was adopted. In this, Japanese education was combined with Western education. In 1908, primary education in Japan became compulsory for 6 years. In 1893, the first vocational college was established. The Constitution adopted in 1946 defined the rights and duties of citizens in the field of education. It stipulates that all children receive free general education. The structure of modern education systems in Japan is as follows: kindergartens, elementary schools, junior high schools, senior high schools, and institutions of higher education.

The US education system

The structure of the education system in the United States of America is as follows: - preschool education institutions where children are educated from 3 to 5 years old; - primary schools up to grades 1-8 (children from 6 to 13 years old study in such schools); - Secondary schools with grades 9-12 (children aged 14-17 are educated in these schools). It consists of a lower and upper stage. The next level of education in the United States of America is higher education, which consists of 2- or 4-year colleges, universities, and postgraduate or doctoral programs. In the US, compulsory education is valid until the age of 16. Educational institutions in this country can be owned by the state, community, private and religious institutions.

Education system in France

France is one of the leading economically developed countries in the world. Its educational systems also have an ancient and rich history. In this country, the Law "On Education" was first adopted in 1955 and in 1975 a number of amendments were made to it. The current "Education Law" of the French state was adopted on July 10, 1989, and its change was caused by changes in the education strategy, reforms in the country's internal foreign policy, economic conditions, the introduction of advanced technologies in foreign pedagogy into the country's educational systems, integration of subjects and caused by others.

The development of the educational system in Germany

It should be noted that Germany's path to the market economy is similar to that of our Republic. After the reunification of the two German states, the work on the reform of education in the former German Democratic Republic is also favorable to our conditions. Germany's main problem in education today is to bring education in the former GDR to the same national standard. First of all, it should be noted that education in Germany is a field respected by the state and society, and it is among the top six economically developed countries of the country. The description of German education systems is as follows: Education system in Germany: Pre-school education system is also considered an important stage in the German education system. It has more than 100 years of history. Kindergartens are considered a lower level of education, but they are not part of the state system. Kindergartens are funded by various public organizations, charitable associations, enterprises, private individuals, and religious institutions. Parents pay a lot of money to kindergartens for the education of their children. 80% of children aged 3 to 6 attend kindergartens. In Germany, children are usually educated in kindergarten until noon.

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